

EFFECTIVE WAYS OF INCREASING LISTENING SKILLS.

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Annotation: The article investigates the importance of increasing listening skills in English. It provides data on different ways of improving listening skill and their usage in practice.

Key words: listening comprehension, the Internet, educational standards, listening strategies, translations, IELTS exam, TOEFL exam, CEFR tests.

Nowadays the world is changing dramatically day by day. People can face with some new inventions in every hour. Meanwhile the role of learning English is also increasing. Undoubtedly, In Uzbekistan more and more attention is directed above mentioned spheres to catch up with the globally developing world. Furthermore, new educational standards are being inserted. In this case, being aware of more about English and listening competence is of great importance.

Communication competence includes four main activities: speaking, listening, reading, and writing. Listening is the most difficult skill for many of our students. But that of the time a person is engaged in communication, approximately 9% is devoted to writing, 16% to reading, 30% to speaking, and 45% to listening. That's why for non-linguistic universities the perfection and development of the speech learning procedure becomes actual especially when

we use academic hours of student independent work (self- study) for this purpose.

Of the four skills of language learning, Listening is commonly regarded as the hardest and most challenging. It, nevertheless, has been overlooked with much less time devoted to its instruction as compared with other language skills, like reading, writing, and speaking. Also, most studies concentrate more on the productive skills of writing and speaking. The focus in most language classrooms is testing practices and more on listening exercises than on teaching the listening skills. Richards and Renandya suggest that one expected purpose behind the approach was that listening abilities may possibly be developed in classrooms while students are exposed to second language encounter during the lecture. Nunan believes that listening is commonly regarded as an increasingly relevant language skill that underscores the necessity of acquiring skills and strategies relevant for the understanding of the spoken language. According to Gilakjani Listening skill is very important in foreign language learning because the key to learn a language is to receive language input. Unfortunately, listening skill is often seen as a passive skill in the classroom, as students seem to sit quietly and listen to conversations. On the other hand, Rost assures that listening is an important means of learning a new language. It is primarily by way of listening that language learners are introduced to a new language, which necessitates and improves the acquisition of their overall second or foreign language skills. If students do not clearly understand what they listen in their language classrooms, they may find it difficult to learn the language which can have a very debilitating effect on their learning of other communicative skills, like speaking, reading, and writing. Moreover, listening is crucial for an effective and meaningful participation in the oral conversation. Rost highlights that there is no spoken language without listening. Students feel lost if they do not comprehend the conversation. This is the reason why language learners lose their confidence, and request constantly for frequent repetitions of the spoken text. Similarly, students in Saudi are rarely accustomed to listening native English language

speakers, which puts them in great difficulty in comprehending English language spoken with its usual pace and pitch. Furthermore, the students selected as subjects of this research have all chosen listening as their preferred language learning skill. Though, there are those who display their strong reading skill, and their aptitude for structured drills and substitution exercises.

Creating and improving listening comprehension requires effective sources to improve listening skills. They are the followings:

Course books with audio CDs,
communications,
songs,
films,
audio books,
podcasts,
radio,
special educational sites

these courses have to be used based on the age group of the learner as well as the level of their English.

Primary school pupils are more tend to learn by listening or watching. Considering this reason teaching them with the help of songs and cartoon is more effective than task based learning.

Elementary students should be taught by listening activities in order to improve listening comprehension. The activities must be “Gap filling”, “Matching” the speaker and the picture. It is more advantageous for them to use course books with CD’s

Mature learners are advised to learn listening acquisition by more serious materials. For instance, podcasts films, audio books, podcasts, radio, special educational sites. Furthermore, adult students can learn easier by authentic materials. It provides effectiveness and speed of the learning process.

Students who are preparing to IELTS exam, TOEFL exam or CEFR tests must use more practice tests. Starting from easies level exercises and increasing

the degree to more difficult practices step by step is regarded to be reliable way of learning listening competence. While listening students understand and analyze the speech simultaneously. That gives the students direct understanding without any translation.

With the help of improving listening students speaking ability also develops.

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